

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Pairing guide of typical dishes from Riobamba city as a tourist information resource

Guía de maridaje de platos típicos de la ciudad de Riobamba como recurso de información turística

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Abstract Riobamba, located in the heart of Ecuador, enchanted visitors with its wide variety of tourist attractions, including majestic volcanoes, mountains, and picturesque towns, as well as its rich gastronomy. The objective of the study was to develop a pairing guide with the city's typical dishes, highlighting its gastronomy and suggesting to diners how to properly pair the dishes with drinks that enhance their flavors. To create the guide, the focus group technique was used, which included 11 participants who, through sensory analysis, rated the best combinations of foods and drinks using a tasting sheet that evaluated harmony, balance, intensity, and the aromatic phase. The qualitative results were divided into categories of drink, aroma, and dish, demonstrating that the pairing influences the gastronomic experience, revealing curious data about the combination of chicha and wine. It was concluded that beer was the most versatile drink to pair with food, thanks to its freshness and flavor, which turned out to be less invasive on the palate. With these results, the pairing guide was created that presented the best drink suggestions for each dish, recommending their distribution in strategic places so that more people could learn about and experience the combination of foods with each suggested drink.

Keywords gastronomy, gastronomic pairing, typical food, sensorial experience, gastronomic tourism.

Resumen Riobamba, ubicada en el corazón de Ecuador, encantó a los visitantes con su amplia variedad de atracciones turísticas, que incluían majestuosos volcanes, montañas y pintorescos pueblos, además de su rica gastronomía. El objetivo del estudio fue desarrollar una guía de maridaje con los platos típicos de la ciudad, destacando su gastronomía y sugiriendo a los comensales cómo maridar adecuadamente los platillos con bebidas que realzaran sus sabores. Para crear la guía, se utilizó la técnica del focus group, que incluyó a 11 participantes que, a través de un análisis sensorial, calificaron las mejores combinaciones de alimentos y bebidas mediante una ficha de cata que evaluó la armonía, el equilibrio, la intensidad y la fase aromática. Los resultados cualitativos se dividieron en categorías de bebida, aroma y plato, lo que demostró que el maridaje influye en la experiencia gastronómica, revelando datos curiosos sobre la combinación de chicha y vino. Se concluyó que la cerveza era la bebida más versátil para maridar con los alimentos, gracias a su frescura y sabor, que resultó ser menos invasivo en el paladar. Con estos resultados, se creó la guía de maridajes que presentaba las mejores sugerencias de bebidas para cada plato, recomendando su distribución en lugares estratégicos para que más personas pudieran conocer y experimentar la combinación de alimentos con cada bebida sugerida.

Palabras clave gastronomía, maridaje, comida típica, experiencia sensorial, turismo gastronómico.

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Introduction

Tourism has been considered one of the most dynamic and exciting industries in the world, acting as a key driver for economic growth, sustainable development, and cultural exchange on a global scale. It is not just about enjoying leisure moments, but also about learning and enriching oneself through visits to historical sites, admiring natural landscapes, and immersing oneself in urban life (Orgaz & Moral, 2016). Tourism encompasses activities undertaken by people who travel and stay in places different from their usual environment, for pleasure, business, or other reasons (Santamaría-Freire & López-Pérez, 2019). Additionally, tourism also includes entertainment and relaxation activities undertaken during free time. In this context, Riobamba stood out for its strategic geographical location in the center of the country, making it an ideal destination for national tourism circuits, being just three hours from Quito and the Amazon, and four hours from Guayaquil and Cuenca.

Riobamba offered a diversity of activities, from adventure sports to natural and gastronomic attractions, including visits to the Cathedral of San Pedro, strolls in the old train station, the Cacha viewpoint, and excursions to the Altar and Chimborazo volcanoes. Despite its culinary richness, based on local ingredients such as potatoes, corn, and quinoa, Riobamba's gastronomic potential was not always fully utilized, as the inadequate pairing of beverages with typical dishes could negatively affect the culinary experience.

Choosing the right beverages was crucial for enhancing flavors and creating harmony in the tasting experience. In light of the loss of part of the local gastronomic culture and the growing influence of globalized cuisine, this research aimed to develop a pairing guide for some of the typical dishes of Riobamba, to boost gastronomic tourism and offer visitors a more enriching culinary experience, balancing flavors between food and beverages.

Materials and methods

The creation of the pairing guide for the traditional dishes of Riobamba was conducted through a qualitative approach focused on the sensory evaluation of flavor and beverage combinations. Sensory tests were conducted to identify synergies and contrasts in taste profiles, textures, and aromas of the selected dishes and beverages. Feedback from local teachers and diners was essential in evaluating the most successful combinations and ensuring that the guide reflected the essence of Riobamba's cuisine.

An inductive method was used to analyze the results of multiple tests, identifying patterns in the combinations of dishes and beverages. The collected data allowed for the discovery of new associations and highlighted the most suitable flavor complements. The focus group technique was imple-

mented through sensory evaluation (Powell & Single, 1996), where qualified professionals assessed the combinations based on flavor intensity, harmony among components, and aromatic notes (Torricco et al., 2023).

The process included participant recruitment, moderation of sessions in a gastronomy laboratory, and the preparation of the final report. Participants, including teachers, students, and local diners, recorded their feedback using tasting sheets. This diversity of opinions contributed to the development of a balanced pairing guide that reflected the preferences of both experts and the public in general.

During the main activity, tasting sheets were provided to participants to gather information on the interaction between the flavors of traditional food and the characteristics of beverages. Aspects such as the influence of the acidity and sweetness of beer, wine, and chicha on the perception of food were explored, as well as how successful pairings could promote traditional gastronomy and encourage local tourism. The report resulting from the focus group was crucial for the research, providing a clear view of participants' opinions and perceptions, as well as identifying trends and needs in the combinations of dishes and beverages.

The tasting sheets, which included information about the taster, the origin of the beverage, and evaluations of visual, olfactory, and taste phases, were key to recording and assessing the results. Three beverages were selected for the study: wine, beer, and chicha. Malbec was described as a versatile red wine, ideal for red meats and cheeses, while lager beer, with its light profile, was considered more suitable for informal pairings. Chicha de jora, with its slightly sweet and acidic flavor, proved to be a valuable option for balancing the richness of the dishes.

The pairing activity involved 11 people, including culinary professionals and students, who participated in an environment designed to foster interaction. Eight dishes were prepared to pair with the selected beverages. To evaluate the aroma of the dishes, values were assigned to the intensity of the aroma, which were summed and averaged among the tasters to determine their ranking.

The pairing guide was created with visually appealing content, using the Canva platform. The brochure included a cover with the title and an introduction about the city and its gastronomy. The combinations were organized in a color-coding system to indicate the quality of the pairings, and the following pages described the beverages and dishes, along with a table that related the beverages to pairing aspects, using the rating colors obtained from the tasters.

Figure 1 presents the interpretation regarding the acceptability of the products according to their intensity, balance, and harmony, using a color code: green for excellent, orange for good, and red for fair. If a taster seeks greater balance, it

is recommended to choose a beverage marked in green. The red and orange squares do not indicate prohibited combinations; instead, they invite tasters to experiment and discover new results. This interpretation applies to all foods in the guide, which concludes with recommendations for the public, academic information from the student, and acknowledgments for reading the document.

Figure 1. Interpretation of product pairings based on their acceptability according to intensity, balance, and harmony.

Results and discussion

The pairing sheets of each participant were analyzed, and records were kept. The tasting sheet evaluated four factors: harmony, balance, intensity, and aroma. A fundamental aspect of developing the pairing guide for Riobamba was assessing how different beverages complement and enhance the flavors of the region’s typical dishes. The results of this evaluation provided valuable insights into the influence of pairings on the culinary experience. Below, the main findings are presented by beverage, highlighting the most suitable combination between one of the eight options and each beverage. Table 1 shows the results for the harmony factor across the three beverages.

In the analysis of the harmony factor, the tripes (intestines) showed greater compatibility with wine, as red wines, with their intense flavors and fruity notes, harmonized well with the juiciness and smoky aromas of roasted meats. Tripes, being an animal-based food, are ideally paired with wine in this phase. Furthermore, the complex flavors of roasted food complemented the nuances of the wine, especially Malbec, whose controlled acidity enhanced the flavors on the palate.

Table 1. Assessment of harmony concerning wine, beer, and chicha

Beverage	Dish	Taster											Total	
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11		
Wine	Pork	Ceviche	2	3	1	3	2	4	4	2	3	2	1	27
		Roast pork	3	1	5	3	4	2	3	2	3	2	2	30
		Guaguamama	2	1	4	3	4	3	2	2	4	3	2	30
		Llapingachos	3	1	4	3	2	1	2	2	4	2	1	25
	Offal	Tripes	4	4	5	2	5	1	3	2	3	4	3	36
		Sweetbreads	3	1	5	3	1	1	3	4	4	2	4	31
	Dessert	Fritters	2	5	3	1	1	5	1	3	2	4	2	29
		Licto biscuits	2	1	2	3	1	3	1	4	4	1	4	26
Beer	Pork	Ceviche	4	5	5	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	48
		Roast pork	4	5	4	5	4	3	3	2	3	4	5	42
		Guaguamama	3	5	5	4	5	3	2	2	3	4	2	38
		Llapingachos	3	5	4	3	3	2	4	3	3	4	4	38
	Offal	Tripes	4	5	5	3	5	2	3	4	4	4	4	43
		Sweetbreads	4	5	5	4	3	2	4	4	4	5	2	42
	Dessert	Fritters	1	1	4	4	2	3	4	3	3	1	1	27
		Licto biscuits	1	1	2	4	1	3	3	4	3	1	2	25
Chicha	Pork	Ceviche	3	3	2	5	2	2	2	2	2	3	5	31
		Roast pork	2	4	1	5	4	1	5	4	3	5	4	38
		Guaguamama	4	4	2	5	3	2	4	3	2	4	3	36
		Llapingachos	3	4	2	5	4	3	5	4	4	5	5	44
	Offal	Tripes	4	5	1	5	4	3	4	3	2	4	5	40
		Sweetbreads	3	5	3	5	3	3	5	4	2	3	4	40
	Dessert	Fritters	2	1	2	5	5	5	5	4	3	5	5	42
		Licto biscuits	2	1	3	5	4	4	5	4	3	5	4	40

In the case of beer, ceviche was the best companion. Its light body and mild flavor, combined with the absence of intense spices in the ceviche, allowed the individual ingredients to be perceived without any one of them dominating. This combination created a pleasant sensory experience. Additionally, the focus group also suggested trying the beer with tripes, sweetbreads, and Roast Pork, although the Biscuit did not have the same acceptance.

On the other hand, chicha was chosen as the best harmonious combination with llapingachos, as the sweet and acidic nuances of the chicha enhanced the mild and earthy flavors of the potatoes, creating a pleasing balance. The thick texture of the chicha contrasted with the softness of the potatoes, of-

fering an interesting experience. It was also suggested to pair it with tripes, sweetbreads, Fritters, and Biscuit, as its versatility allowed it to complement the flavors of various dishes without overshadowing them. Table 2 displays the results by tasters regarding the balance in relation to the beverages.

The balance generated a pleasant experience on the palate, where the food and beverages complemented each other without competing. The tripes and wine stood out as the most appreciated combination, as the wine, commonly consumed with roasted meats, enhanced the flavors of the tripes. Guaguamamas and sweetbreads took second and third place, with their scores influenced by the preparation of the food, such as the spices and cooking techniques.

Table 2. Evaluation of balance concerning wine, beer, and chicha

Beverage	Dish	Taster										Total		
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10		11	
Wine	Pork	Ceviche	2	3	1	3	3	3	3	2	4	2	1	27
		Roast pork	3	1	5	3	4	2	3	1	3	3	1	29
		Guaguamama	3	1	5	3	4	2	3	2	3	3	3	32
		Llapingachos	3	1	4	2	2	1	2	2	4	2	2	25
	Offal	Tripes	3	4	5	2	5	1	3	2	3	3	2	33
		Sweetbreads	4	1	5	3	1	2	2	3	4	2	4	31
	Dessert	Fritters	1	5	4	1	1	4	1	2	2	4	2	27
		Licto biscuits	1	1	2	3	1	4	1	3	3	1	4	24
Beer	Pork	Ceviche	4	5	4	5	5	4	5	3	4	4	5	48
		Roast pork	4	5	5	5	4	3	4	2	3	5	5	45
		Guaguamama	4	5	5	4	5	4	2	2	2	4	1	38
		Llapingachos	2	5	4	4	3	3	3	2	3	4	4	37
	Offal	Tripes	4	5	5	4	5	2	2	4	4	4	4	43
		Sweetbreads	4	5	5	4	3	3	5	4	4	4	2	43
	Dessert	Fritters	1	1	3	4	2	4	2	2	3	1	1	24
		Licto biscuits	1	1	2	4	1	4	3	4	3	2	1	26
Chicha	Pork	Ceviche	3	3	3	5	2	1	2	3	2	5	4	33
		Roast pork	3	4	2	5	3	1	4	3	3	5	4	37
		Guaguamama	3	4	3	5	3	3	4	3	2	4	4	38
		Llapingachos	3	4	2	5	5	4	5	4	3	5	5	45
	Offal	Tripes	3	5	1	5	4	4	5	4	2	5	4	42
		Sweetbreads	3	5	3	5	3	3	5	3	2	4	4	40
	Dessert	Fritters	2	1	2	5	5	5	5	3	3	5	5	41
		Licto biscuits	2	1	4	5	4	4	5	4	2	5	3	39

Regarding ceviche, it maintained its association with beer, where both complemented each other harmoniously. The beer, especially the lighter and refreshing varieties, contrasted with the acidity of the ceviche, helping to cleanse the palate between bites and maintaining a sense of freshness. It was also suggested that Roast Pork and tripes could pair well with beer, creating new experiences depending on their preparation.

The balance between chicha and llapingachos was notable, thanks to the mix of sweet flavors from the chicha and the savory flavors from the llapingachos. Additionally, tripes and sweetbreads also achieved a good balance with chicha due to the spices present in the food and the beverage. The scores remained within an acceptable range, demonstrating the versatility of chicha. However, ceviche had little acceptance with this beverage due to the combination of the chicha's fermentation and the tomato juice, resulting in an

acidic or bitter flavor. For an ideal balance, it was suggested to pair tripes with wine, ceviche de chochos with beer, and llapingachos with chicha. Table 3 shows the intensity of the beverages.

In the intensity factor, the tripes maintained their relationship with wine, as both exhibited intense aromas and flavors

that, when combined, created satisfaction on the palate. The wine also contrasted acceptably with guaguamama, sweetbreads, and Fritters, although the intensity of the combination depended on the preparation of each dish. The scores did not exceed 40 points, indicating that in some cases, the beverage was perceived as invasive.

Table 3. Evaluation of intensity regarding wine, beer, and chicha

Beverage	Dish	Taster											Total	
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11		
Wine	Pork	Ceviche	3	3	1	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	1	28
		Roast pork	3	1	4	3	5	1	3	3	4	2	1	30
		Guaguamama	2	1	4	4	4	2	3	3	4	2	3	32
		Llapingachos	3	1	3	2	3	2	2	4	4	2	1	27
	Offal	Tripes	2	4	5	2	5	2	3	3	5	2	4	37
		Sweetbreads	3	1	5	3	1	1	3	4	4	2	4	31
	Dessert	Fritters	2	5	3	1	1	4	5	3	2	3	3	32
		Licto biscuits	1	1	1	3	1	4	5	3	4	1	3	27
Beer	Pork	Ceviche	3	5	5	5	5	4	5	4	4	3	5	48
		Roast pork	5	5	4	4	4	2	3	3	2	5	4	41
		Guaguamama	3	5	5	4	5	3	2	2	3	4	3	39
		Llapingachos	3	5	4	4	4	2	4	3	3	3	4	39
	Offal	Tripes	4	5	5	4	5	2	3	3	5	4	5	45
		Sweetbreads	4	5	5	4	3	2	4	3	4	3	3	40
	Dessert	Fritters	1	1	4	4	2	3	5	3	3	1	1	28
		Licto biscuits	1	1	1	4	1	4	3	3	3	3	1	25
Chicha	Pork	Ceviche	3	3	1	5	2	3	2	2	1	3	4	29
		Roast pork	2	4	1	5	3	3	3	3	1	5	5	35
		Guaguamama	4	4	2	5	3	4	4	2	2	4	3	37
		Llapingachos	2	4	2	5	5	2	3	3	3	5	4	38
	Offal	Tripes	2	5	1	5	4	3	2	2	2	5	5	36
		Sweetbreads	3	5	3	5	3	4	5	3	2	4	3	40
	Dessert	Fritters	2	1	2	5	5	5	5	3	2	5	5	40
		Licto biscuits	1	1	3	5	4	4	5	2	2	5	2	34

Beer also played an important role in intensity, especially with ceviche, since both are consumed cold, which contributed to their acceptability on the palate. In contrast, the Biscuit were not compatible with beer, as reflected in the scores. Guaguamama and sweetbreads were acceptable options when paired with beer, producing similar sensations on the palate.

Chicha scored well in intensity, being one of the best options to accompany Fritters, due to its ability to create a pleasant balance on the palate with its slightly sweet and acidic flavors. It also enhanced the perception of umami flavor in the sweetbreads, providing a refreshing and balanced contrast. Although it did not fully highlight the flavors of the dishes, it did not detract from them.

In summary, for the intensity factor, the most suitable combinations were tripes with wine, ceviche de chochos with beer, and sweetbreads and Fritters with chicha, as these combinations received the highest scores in the sensory evaluation. Table 4 shows the results for the aroma of the beverages.

The table presented the scores assigned to the aroma, classifying it as high, medium, or low. According to the results in Table 4, it was observed that wine did not enhance the aroma of any food group, including pork, offal, or desserts. However, the tripes showed a medium aroma when paired with the beverage, which supported the previous results. The creation of a pairing guide for typical dishes from Riobamba revealed an intriguing challenge: the low aromatic harmony of certain

Table 4. Evaluation of aroma regarding wine, beer, and chicha

Beverage	Dish	Taster											Total	Analysis	
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11			
Wine	Pork	Ceviche	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	3	1	18	Bajo
		Roast pork	2	1	3	1	2	1	1	1	2	3	1	18	Bajo
		Guaguamama	2	1	3	1	3	2	3	1	2	1	2	21	Bajo
		Llapingachos	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	3	1	2	16	Bajo
	Offal	Tripes	2	3	3	1	3	1	2	1	2	2	2	22	Medio
		Sweetbreads	2	1	3	1	1	2	2	2	3	1	2	20	Bajo
	Dessert	Fritters	1	3	2	2	1	3	1	2	1	2	1	19	Bajo
		Licto biscuits	1	1	1	3	1	2	1	1	3	1	2	17	Bajo
Beer	Pork	Ceviche	3	3	3	2	3	2	3	2	3	2	2	28	Medio
		Roast pork	3	3	3	2	3	2	3	2	2	2	3	28	Medio
		Guaguamama	2	3	3	2	3	3	1	1	2	2	2	24	Medio
		Llapingachos	2	3	3	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	23	Medio
	Offal	Tripes	3	3	3	2	3	2	2	2	3	3	3	29	Medio
		Sweetbreads	3	3	3	3	2	3	2	2	3	2	2	28	Medio
	Dessert	Fritters	1	1	1	3	1	3	1	2	1	1	2	17	Bajo
		Licto biscuits	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	14	Bajo
Chicha	Pork	Ceviche	2	2	2	3	1	3	2	2	2	3	2	24	Medio
		Roast pork	1	3	1	3	2	2	2	1	1	3	3	22	Medio
		Guaguamama	2	2	1	3	2	2	3	2	1	2	1	21	Bajo
		Llapingachos	1	2	3	3	3	2	2	3	2	3	2	26	Medio
	Offal	Tripes	2	3	1	3	3	2	2	2	1	3	3	25	Medio
		Sweetbreads	2	3	1	3	2	3	3	3	1	2	2	25	Medio
	Dessert	Fritters	2	1	2	2	3	3	3	3	2	3	2	26	Medio
		Licto biscuits	2	1	2	3	3	2	3	2	2	3	1	24	Medio

wines with these authentic dishes. Although wine is a classic pairing beverage, some wines, especially those with strong tannins or very fruity whites, may have aromatic profiles that compete with the flavors of local dishes.

Regarding beer, the data showed that, when combined with most foods, it maintained a medium rating, indicating that the aromas of pork and offal-based products were pleasant to the tasters. This was because the aroma of the beer was not invasive, allowing for the enjoyment of the aromas of both foods. In contrast, desserts maintained a low aroma rating, as they are not typically associated with beer due to their sweet and acidic odors. Beer proved to be more acceptable during pairing, which could serve as a reference for future research.

In terms of chicha, it showed greater compatibility with most products, including pork, offal, and desserts. Its slightly sweet aroma allowed for a pleasant aromatic fusion for the tasters, although cultural factors may also have influenced this. However, guaguamama stood out as the exception, scoring the lowest, likely due to its strong aroma, which made it difficult to recognize the scents of the chicha.

The most suitable combinations between different types of

beverages and typical dishes from Riobamba were highlighted, showing that both wine, beer, and chicha reached a medium level in their respective pairings. The wine was noted as the best option to accompany tripes, suggesting that its aromatic profile complements this dish adequately. On the other hand, beer proved to be suitable for pork and offal dishes, offering a harmonious combination that enhances the flavors of these foods. Chicha, while compatible with pork, offal, and desserts, showed a notable exception with guaguamama, indicating that its strong aroma could interfere with the subtler flavors of this beverage. Overall, the results suggest that these combinations are not only valid but can also enrich the gastronomic experience of diners by considering the balance and harmony of flavors in each pairing.

The three phases were analyzed based on the foods and which beverage enhances their flavor. Evaluation of typical dishes from Riobamba based on intensity, balance, and harmony with different beverages is shown in Table 5. The richness of the regional cuisine and the versatility of pairing options were revealed.

Table 5. Evaluation of intensity, balance, and harmony regarding wine, beer, and chicha

Indicador	Plato	Vino	Cerveza	Chicha		
Intensity	Pork	Ceviche	28	48	29	
		Roast pork	30	41	35	
		Guaguamama	32	39	37	
		Llapingachos	27	39	38	
	Offal	Tripes	37	45	36	
		Sweetbreads	31	40	40	
	Dessert	Fritters	32	28	40	
		Licto biscuits	27	25	34	
	Balance	Pork	Ceviche	27	48	33
			Roast pork	29	45	37
Guaguamama			32	38	38	
Llapingachos			25	37	45	
Offal		Tripes	33	43	42	
		Sweetbreads	31	43	40	
Dessert		Fritters	27	24	41	
		Licto biscuits	24	26	39	
Harmony		Pork	Ceviche	27	48	31
			Roast pork	30	42	38
	Guaguamama		30	38	36	
	Llapingachos		25	38	44	
	Offal	Tripes	36	43	40	
		Sweetbreads	31	42	40	
	Dessert	Fritters	29	27	42	
		Licto biscuits	26	25	40	

The table showed that beer topped the list of suggestions, pairing best with six of the eight tasted dishes due to its intensity. Chicha stood out by complementing three dishes, including both desserts and the Sweetbreads. As for wine, it was suggested to try it with the tripes, as its score was in a similar range to that of other foods.

Overall, it was evident that wine maintained low scores compared to beer and chicha, indicating that this beverage did not enhance the flavors of the foods due to its overwhelming intensity. Additionally, beer was observed to re-

main the best option for achieving a balance of flavors with ceviche, roast pork, guaguamama, tripes, and Sweetbreads. Chicha also proved effective when paired with llapingachos, Fritters, and Biscuit. For wine, guaguamama was the best recommendation, given its scoring range similar to that of other beverages.

Finally, both beer and chicha demonstrated a greater ability to enhance the flavors of the dishes, creating pleasant sensations on the palate without one flavor overpowering another. In contrast, the biscuits, fritters, and ceviche received

Table 6. Proposals for the best pairings based on harmony, balance, and intensity

Beverage	Option	Harmony	Balance	Intensity
Wine	1	Tripes	Tripes	Tripes
	2	Sweetbreads	Guaguamama	Guaguamama
	3	Roast pork/Guaguamama	Sweetbreads	Fritters
Beer	1	Ceviche	Ceviche	Ceviche
	2	Tripes	Roast pork	Tripes
	3	Roast pork/Sweetbreads	Tripes/Sweetbreads	Roast pork
Chicha	1	Llapingachos	Llapingachos	Sweetbreads
	2	Fritters	Tripes	Fritters
	3	Tripes/Sweetbreads/Biscuit	Fritters	Llapingachos

low scores, reflecting the influence of their ingredients and components on the rating. The harmony of the foods with the beverages continued to show that beer and chicha were the most suitable for providing a pleasurable experience on the palate, maintaining scores above 40. Table 6 presents the top three pairing suggestions for beverages that optimally accompany each dish based on harmony, balance, and intensity.

The table presents a comparative evaluation of three beverages -wine, beer, and chichi- concerning their ability to complement different dishes, considering three criteria: harmony, balance, and intensity. In the case of wine, tripes stand out as the best pairing across all three parameters, suggesting that this food has a notable interaction with the characteristics of the wine. On the other hand, guaguamama and Sweetbreads also stand out in terms of harmony and balance, although with less consistency compared to tripes.

Beer, for its part, is presented as a versatile option, with ceviche taking the top spot in harmony, highlighting its compatibility with this fresh dish. However, beer also performs strongly with tripes and Roast Pork, suggesting it can be a good choice for more intense dishes. Regarding chicha, its greatest potential is observed with llapingachos and Fritters, emphasizing the adaptability of this beverage to local cuisine. Together, the results reflect a rich interaction between the beverages and the foods, where choosing the right drink can enhance the gastronomic experience by providing an optimal balance of flavors.

Conclusions

The research resulted in the creation of the “Guide to Pairings of Typical Dishes from the City of Riobamba.” This guide recommends the best beverages to accompany each dish, promoting local culinary culture for both residents and tourists. A lack of pairing culture in the region was evident, underscoring the importance of educating the population about beverages that enhance food flavors. Beer was one of the best options for enhancing flavors, although wine and chicha also stood out as valid alternatives. Furthermore, the guide, visually appealing and easy to understand, celebrates the culinary culture of Riobamba, encourages experimentation in pairings, and supports gastronomic tourism while respecting the region’s traditions.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Author contributions

Jessica P. Chaglla and Carolina G. Herrera: Conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, supervision, validation, visualization, drafting the original manuscript and writing, review, and editing.

Data availability statement

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Statement on the use of AI

The authors acknowledge the use of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies to improve the readability and clarity of the article.

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